

Chemical Examination of the Roots of *Hygrophyla Spinosa*.

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Hygrophyla Spinosa (Sanskrit—Kokiláksha, Bengali—Kuliámára. Hindi—Tálmákhána) of the natural order of *Acanthaceæ*, is an annual marshy herb with an ascending rhizome and numerous stout, erect and unbranched stem, two to five feet long. The stems are somewhat compressed and thickened at the nodes with numerous long hairs below each node. The leaves are sessile and six at each node—the two outer ones 4—5 inches long and the four inner ones 1½ inches in length—each having a sharp yellow spine, one inch long. The flowers are bright blue in colour with an occasional white specimen, and generally eight at each node. The roots are creamy yellow in colour, thin, tapering and tubular, with numerous rootlets, possessing a peculiar marshy odour and a slimy cooling taste.

Hygrophyla spinosa has always occupied a prominent place in Hindu Materia Medica. The roots are considered to be cooling, diuretic, strengthening and stimulating and specially efficacious in dropsical cases and 'gravelish affections.' Mohammedan writers also mention the use of the plant for the same purpose and also for its external application in the form of a poultice or embrocation in rheumatism. In the Pharmacopoeia of India, several European writers also bear testimony to the excellent diuretic properties of the roots of the plant.

The roots were first examined by Warden (*Pharmacographica Indica*, Vol. III, p. 38), who by extraction with 80% alcohol, isolated a crystalline substance apparently in an impure form, which has been described as a mass of cauliflower-like nodules, nearly white in colour and contaminated with a trace of oil. It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellow colour.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to submit it to a thorough and systematic examination. The roots of the plant on extraction with rectified spirit and

subsequent distillation of the solvent yielded a crystalline substance contaminated with a sticky, green wax and a pale yellow oil. The waxy and oily impurities were eliminated by boiling the mass with saturated alcoholic potash and precipitation by water. The substance thus recovered on repeated crystallisations from dilute alcohol was obtained in the form of fine snow-white needles with silky lustre, melting at 194° . This substance was found to have the molecular formula $C_{28}H_{46}O$, and gave all the reactions of phytosterols. Thus it must be a member of the phytosterol family having the general formula $C_nH_{2n-10}O$, of which only one isolated example appears to exist in literature containing twentyeight carbon atoms, *viz.*, that furnished by Henry (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1624), who claims to have isolated a phytosterol $C_{28}H_{46}O$, from *Hyenanche globosa*.

The properties of the phytosterol isolated by the present authors in course of this investigation are quite in line with the general properties of the phytosterols of the above family and so evidently it is quite different from the phytosterol isolated by Henry which had a negative rotation $[\alpha]_D^{15} = -22.4^{\circ}$. Thus it gave an acetyl derivative melting at 208° and having a rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{28} = +27.8^{\circ}$ in chloroform. This substance has been named "hygrosterol" by the present authors. One acetyl, two bromo- and one chloro-derivatives as also a digitonide of the substance have been prepared and described in the Experimental; the carbanilate and the benzoyl derivatives were unsuccessful.

Besides the above mentioned hygrosterol, the roots of *H. spinosa* on further examination, yielded a trace of an essential oil, a yellowish-green wax, a sticky gum and a comparatively large quantity of maltose. The ash obtained from the roots on ignition was found to consist mostly of potassium salts.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The fresh roots of *Hygrophyla spinosa* procured locally were washed free from mud and dirt, cut up into small pieces by means of a chopping machine, sun-dried and extracted in 50 gram-lots by various solvents in a Soxhlet's apparatus. The solvent was subsequently evaporated. A preliminary examination of the root by the

usual methods indicated the presence of an enzyme in traces and absence of alkaloids.

Petroleum ether extract (1.05%).—Pale greenish-yellow oil containing a few colourless needle-shaped crystals. The amount of the latter was too small to be isolated, but from the appearance it seemed to be hygrosterol.

Carbon tetrachloride extract (1.2%).—Greenish-white substance having a waxy consistency and greasy feel. The product on repeated crystallisation from alcohol was obtained in the form of needle-shaped, radiating clusters which were still soft and greasy to the touch and melted indefinitely between 50° and 90°. It gave the colour reactions of hygrosterol, but apparently was in an impure condition.

Benzene extract (1.4%).—Soft greenish-white wax with properties similar to the above.

Chloroform extract (1.65%).—Pale green wax admixed with a trace of an yellow oil. Properties similar to the above. The green colour was due to the presence of traces of chlorophyll.

Carbon disulphide extract (1.73%).—Pale green wax with properties similar to the above.

Acetone extract (2.2%).—Dark brown sticky substance with a powerful aromatic odour. Fehling's solution was rapidly reduced and on distillation in steam it yielded a trace of volatile oil. Apparently the substance was contaminated with sugar.

Alcoholic extract (4.8%).—Pale green sticky wax, reducing Fehling's solution rather rapidly. On examination it was found to contain 1.7% of reducing and 2.4% of total sugars estimated as glucose. This was the extract which gave the largest yield of hygrosterol, and consequently the operation was repeated on a large scale.

3 Kg. of the dried and chopped roots were extracted with 6 litres of rectified spirit in a large extraction apparatus by boiling for eight hours. The extract was allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature for 24 hours, when a large quantity of a brownish-white precipitate collected at the bottom. The clear supernatant liquid was siphoned off and the precipitate filtered and washed with a little absolute alcohol. It was first dried in a steam-oven and then in a vacuum desiccator. The substance (38 g.) was purified by repeated crystallisation from 80% alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal and finally obtained as fine, colourless, stout prisms melting between

100° and 110° with charring and decomposition. The osazone which was prepared by the usual method melted at 206° and was found to be identical with maltosazone. Thus the substance was maltose.

The alcoholic mother-liquor from the above substance was distilled from a water-bath until alcohol ceased to come over. The syrupy product on distillation in steam yielded an opalescent distillate from which ether extracted a trace of a pale yellow oil with a peculiar aromatic odour. The quantity however was too insufficient for any systematic examination.

The residue after steam distillation was filtered and washed several times with hot water. The filtrate was greenish-yellow in colour, slightly acid towards litmus and reduced Fehling's solution very readily. It contained a fair amount of reducing sugars, mainly glucose and maltose.

The residue from the above operation (29 g.) on drying, was found to be contaminated with an yellow oil, which could not be eliminated by spreading the substance on a porous plate. On extraction with petroleum ether the product was divided into two fractions, namely, a major fraction (17 g.) which was a colourless crystalline solid having only a slightly sticky feel, and a minor fraction (12 g.) which was an exceedingly sticky greenish-yellow wax. The crystalline solid was recrystallised several times from dilute alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal and finally obtained in the form of colourless glistening needles melting at 194°. It gave all the characteristic colour reactions for phytosterol with concentrated sulphuric acid in presence of iodine, chloroform and acetic anhydride. It showed a rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{28} = +27.8^\circ$ in chloroform. (Found: C, 84.06; H, 11.6; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 396. $C_{28}H_{46}O$ requires C, 84.42; H, 11.55 per cent.; M.W., 398).

The greenish-yellow wax mentioned above could not be induced to crystallise from any solvent under any condition. Under the microscope it was found to consist of colourless needles (resembling those of hygrosterol) embedded in a matrix of tenacious greenish-yellow wax which apparently prevented the isolation of the former. The substance was therefore refluxed on the water-bath with ten times its weight of saturated alcoholic potash for three hours, when it completely went into solution with a reddish-brown colour. The solution was diluted with an equal volume of hot water and the liquid allowed to cool, when a mass of colourless crystals separated out. These were filtered off and recrystallised from dilute alcohol

when colourless glistening needles, m. p. 194° , were obtained, and were found to be identical with hygrosterol already described. The alcoholic mother-liquor on large dilution with water became turbid with separation of minute yellow globules which could not be induced to solidify. The quantity also was too insufficient for further examination.

Acetylhygrosterol.—Hygrosterol (1.5 g.) was heated under reflux for one hour with an excess of acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. On pouring into water and stirring for some time, the acetyl derivative separated in colourless flocks which were collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol in small needle-shaped crystals melting at 208° . (Found : C, 81.52 ; H, 11.22. $C_{28}H_{45}O \cdot CO \cdot CH_3$ requires C, 81.81 ; H, 10.91 per cent.).

Hygrosterol Hydrobromide.—Hygrosterol contains a double linkage and so it readily adds on hydrogen bromide and bromine. The hydrogen bromide addition product was prepared by heating 0.8 g. of the substance with 3 c.c. of fuming hydrobromic acid in a tightly-closed Florence flask on the water-bath for six hours. After cooling the flask was carefully opened and the contents washed out with water and filtered. The crystalline residue was recrystallised from a mixture of alcohol and chloroform (3:1) and obtained in the form of yellowish-white microscopic needles melting at 59° . (Found : Br, 16.32. $C_{28}H_{47}OBr$ requires Br, 16.66 per cent.).

Dibromohygrosterol dibromide.—Hygrosterol (1.4 g.) dissolved in 30 c.c. of chloroform was treated with a chloroform solution of bromine, until the latter was in excess. On allowing the mixture to stand for about 12 hours, the original dark red colour of the solution faded to pale yellow and hydrobromic acid fumes were evolved. The excess of bromine and the solvent were driven away from the mixture by passing a rapid current of air, and the sticky yellow solid crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and chloroform in the form of yellow microscopic needles, m. p. $138-139^{\circ}$ (yield, 1.3 g.). (Found : Br, 44.81. $C_{28}H_{44}OBr_2$ requires Br, 44.66 per cent.).

Action of Thionyl Chloride on Hygrosterol.—Hygrosterol (0.8 g.) and thionyl chloride (2 c.c.) were heated on the water-bath for one hour. On allowing it to stand for about 12 hours, the reaction product completely solidified. It was then crystallised a number of times from a mixture of alcohol and chloroform (3:1) and finally obtained in the form of yellowish-brown prism melting at $101-103^{\circ}$. Besides chlorine, the substance was found to contain sulphur as well

which could not be eliminated under any conditions. Consequently it was not analysed.

Hygrosterol-digitonide.—This was prepared according to the method of Windaus (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 240) by mixing a hot solution of 1 g. of digitonin in 100 c.c. of 90% alcohol with a solution of 0.4 g. of hygrosterol in 60 c.c. of 95% alcohol. As nothing separated on allowing the mixture to stand, the solution was evaporated to about half its bulk and cooled when a quantity of fine white needles separated out. These were filtered, washed with 80% alcohol and dried at 120°. The substance had no definite melting point, but it decomposed between 220° and 230°. (Found: C, 61.42; H, 9.39. $C_{28}H_{46}O \cdot C_{55}H_{94}O_{28}$ requires C, 62.25; H, 8.75 per cent.)

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